

22nd April, 2022

TO WHOMSOEVER IT MAY CONCERN

This is to certify that Mr. Manish Tara, student from Srinivas University, Mangalore, has undergone Industrial Training at Sheraton Grand Bangalore Hotel at Brigade Gateway from 13th December 2021 to 13th April 2022.

We wish him all the very best in his future endeavors.

Namratha B
Assistant Manager - Human Resources

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